

O`ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA BOG`LOVCHILAR SEMANTIKASI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada o`zbek va ingliz tillarida bog`lovchilarning ahamiyati, ularning qo`llanilishi va semantikasi kabi masalalar ko`rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so`zlar: *Bog`lovchi, semantika, ingliz tili, o`zbek tili, vazifa.*

Аннотация: *В этой статье обсуждаются такие вопросы, как важность союзов, их использование и семантика в узбекском и английском языках.*

Ключевые слова: *Союз, семантика, английский, узбекский, задача.*

Abstract: *In this article the issues such as the importance of conjunctions, their usage and semantics in Uzbek and English languages are discussed.*

Key words: *Conjunction, semantics, English, Uzbek, task.*

Hozirgi zamon ingliz tilida bog`lovchilar yordamchi so`z turkumlariga kirsada, lekin gap strukturasi katta o`rin tutadi. Bog`lovchilar bu yordamchi so`z turkumi bo`lib, gap bo`laklarini yoki qo`shma gapning qismlarini bog`lash uchun xizmat qiladi. Bog`lovchilar gap bo`laklari va qo`shma gapning sodda gapning teng qismlari orasidagi turlicha aloqalarni grammatik munosabatni ko`rsatadi.

Gap bo`laklari va gaplar orasidagi grammatik munosabat bog`lovchilar yordamida ifodalansa ham, bog`lovchilarning o`zi bu so`zlarning grammatik formasigato`g`ridan to`g`ri ta`sir ko`rsatmaydi, ular bilan birlashmaydi. Bog`lovchilar tuzilishi jihatidan quyidagi guruhlariga bo`linadi:

a) sodda bog`lovchilar (Simple Conjunctions): and, but, as, or, nor, after, till, that, so, for, hence, yet, since, when, if, lest, while, whether.

b) yasama bog`lovchilar (Derivative Conjunctions): untill, unless, supposing, seeing, provided, because, once, directly, before, consequently.

c) qo`shma bog`lovchilar (Compound Conjunctions): however, wherever,

although, whereas, nevertheless, therefore,

d) murakkab bog'lovchilar (Composite Conjunctions): as well as, both ... and, either... or, neither ... nor, whether ... or, as ... as, as ... so, so ... as, so ... that, rather ... than, such ... as, in order ... that, even though, even if, not so ... as, no sooner ... than, not only ... but, the ... the, no matter ..., who (when), such ... that, but that, or else.

Yuqorida, bog'lovchilarga berilgan ta'rifga ko'ra, birinchi navbatda predlog bilan bog'lovchilar o'rtasidagi farqni anglay olishimiz lozim[16]. Ayrim olimlar esa, bog'lovchilar faqatgina so'zlarni (yoki gap bo'laklarini) bir-biriga bog'laydi, va bog'lovchilar faqat gap strukturasi ma'no anglatishiga yordam beradi, bog'lovchining o'zi hech qanday ma'noga ega emas, degan fikrni ilgari surishadi. Bu fikrga qarama qarshi rus tilshunosi B.A.Ilysh shunday misollar keltiradi:

He came **because** it was late. He came **though** it was late.

Bu gaplardagi **because** va **though** bog'lovchilari ikki ekstralingvistik hodisalar o'rtasidagi aniq har xil ma'nodagi bog'liqlikni yaqqol ko'rsatib beradi: his coming and its being late. Bu gaplardagi kauzal (sabab) bog'lanish tilning tashqi tomonidan mavjud va shu bilan birga ikkinchi gapda konsessiv (to'siqsizlik) bog'lanish ifoda etiladi. Demak, keltirilgan ikkala misolning grammatik strukturasi hech qanday farq yo'q: farqlanish esa bu misollarning ma'nosida, ya'ni bog'lovchilarning ma'nosidadir. Quyidagi misollarda ham bu kabi farqni kuzatish mumkin:

We will come to see you before he comes back, va We will come to see you after he comes back¹.

Bu misollardan ko'rinib turibdiki, har bir bog'lovchi o'z ma'nosiga ega, shu bilan birga ayrim bog'lanishni ifoda etadi, yoki ikki ekstralingvistik hodisalar o'rtasida paydo bo'ladi. Shunday qilib, bog'lovchi va predlog o'rtasidagi farqni aniqlaymiz. Predloglar haqida so'z yuritganimizda, ko'p hollarda ular o'zidan oldin keladigan so'z ma'nosiga ta'sir ko'rsatadilar: misol uchun, –depend fe'li faqatgina –on

¹ Hornby A.S. — Oxford student's dictionary of current English | ox.un.press 2015

yoki –upon, –characteristic sifat so’zi –of predlogi bilan kelganda to’liq bir ma’noga ega bo’la oladi, xolos. Bu misollar ko’rinib turibdiki, predloglar yakka holda hech qanday ma’no anglatmaydi. Bog’lovchilarning gapda ishlatilishidan ma’nosi saqlanib qoladi va mustaqil bo’ladi.

Bog’lovchilar vazifasiga ko’ra teng bog’lovchi va ergashtiruvchi bog’lovchilarga bo’linadi.

Teng bog’lovchilar (Coordinating Conjunction) o’z navbatida quyidagi kichik guruhlariga bo’linadi:

a) Biriktiruvchi bog’lovchilar (Copulative Conjunctions): and, as well as, both ... and, not only ... but, neither ... nor, the ... the .

She dances very hard **and** you’ll be the fresher.

U zo’r raqsga tushadi va sen undan zavq olasan.

You must ask Edmund **and** Lilian they’ll be back in half an hour.

Siz Edmund va Liliandan ularning yarim soatdan keyin qaytish-qaytmasliklarini so’rashingiz kerak.

You are **neither** a friend **nor** a servant.

Siz na sodiq do’stsiz, na ishonchli yordamchi.

b) Ayiruvchi bog’lovchilar (Disjunctive Conjunction): or, either ... or, or else. She ought to marry an American **or** a Portuguese. (HEH32)

U yo Amerikalikka, yo Partugaliyalikka turmushga chiqishi kerak.

Does I mean that they `ve been left well off, **or** that they wish to be under no obligations?

Demoqchimanki, ular tinchgina chiqib ketishdimi, yo o’z burchlarini bajarishmoqchi emasmi?

2. Ergashtiruvchi bog’lovchilar (Subordinating Conjunctions).

Ergashtiruvchi bog’lovchilar ko’pincha ega, kesim, aniqlovchi va hol ergash gaplarni bosh gapga bog’lashga xizmat qiladi. Bundan tashqari ular har xil

konstruksiyalarni ham o'zarobog'lashi mumkin².

Ergashtiruvchi bog'lovchilar ega, kesim va ob'ektiv konstruksiyalarni bog'lab keluvchi **that**, *if*, *whether* kabi bog'lovchilarga bo'linadi:

It was the crew **that** troubled me

Meni tashvishga solgan narsa ekipaj edi.

He showed me in a moment **that** they were just the sort of fresh water swabs we had to fear in an adventure of impotence.

I know of my own knowledge **that** he was a banker account which has never been overdrawn.

Whether he was there then is still enigma.

Uning u yerda bor-yo'qligi hanuz noma'lum.

O'zbek tilshunosligida esa teng bog'lovchilar biriktiruv, zidlov va ayiruv bog'lovchilariga bo'linadi.

1) biriktiruv bog'lovchilar guruhiga *va*, *hamda*, *bilan*, *ham* kabi so'zlar kiradi. Bu bog'lovchilar gapning uyushiq bo'laklarini, qo'shma gap tarkibidagi sodda gaplarni bir-biriga bog'laydi. Biriktiruv bog'lovchisi *va* eng ko'p qo'llanadigan bog'lovchidir.

2) zidlov bog'lovchilari guruhiga *biroq*, *ammo*, *lekin*, *balki*, *holbuki* kabi so'zlar kiradi. Bu bog'lovchilar mazmunan bir-biriga qarama-qarshi qo'yilgan bo'laklarni yoki gaplarni bog'lash uchun xizmat qiladi.

3) ayiruv bog'lovchilar guruhiga *yo*, *yoki*, *yo...*, *yo*, *yoxud*, *dam...*, *dam*, *goh...*, *goh*, *xoh...*, *xoh*, *ba'zan...*, *ba'zan*, *bir-bir* kabi so'zlar kiradi.

Xulosa o'rnida aytish mumkinki, bog'lovchilar semantikasini o'rganish ham o'zbek, ham ingliz tili tilshunosligining ajralmas qismi hisoblanadi. O'rganib chiqilgan misollardan namoyon bo'ldiki, ikki tilda ham bog'lovchilarning tarkibiy qismlarga bo'linishida o'xshashliklar mavjud ekan.

² R.Ikromova, D.Muhamedova, M.Hamrayev. Ona tilidan mashqlar to'plami. (o'quv qo'llanma). TDPU, Toshkent, 2019-yil.

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